

TCAD Analysis of Self Heating in AlGaN/GaN HEMTs under Pulsed Conditions

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I. Purpose

The purpose of this work was to develop a TCAD device model to study the electrical and thermal characteristics of the AlGaN/GaN HEMT in the time domain in contrast to a DC thermal equilibrium analysis. We first examined a channel temperature technique that utilizes temperature dependence of gate voltage on gate current to predict channel temperature. The predicted channel temperature of Method 3104 of MIL-STD 750D is then compared to the simulated temperature profile to determine the corresponding temperature location in the HEMT structure.. Second, we investigated the performance of single and multiple pulses effects on heating of the HEMT. Third, we studied and compared the heating between the DC analysis and a RF transient (multiple pulses) analysis with the same average device power. Finally, we observed large temperature gradients in the device in initial device heating not capable of being observed with conventional DC TCAD analysis.

II. Background

To predict GaN HEMT reliability effects that may be dependent on thermal gradients, the ability to model and validate electrical characteristics over temperature in RF applications is critical. Several researchers are utilizing TCAD device simulators to investigate electrical and thermal effects on compound semiconductor FETs [1,2] but only under DC conditions. Prior efforts by McGlone et al utilized the Silvaco ATLAS© 2-D device simulator to model self-heating of an AlGaN/GaN HEMT on diamond substrates by investigating the dependence of GaN mobility models and thermal resistance on the DC characteristics [2]. This effort which uses the same Silvaco ATLAS tools is a summary of results from Wang's master's thesis [3].

III. Approach

The device model used in this work is identical to that used in McGlone's work [2] which modeled Al-GaN/GaN HEMTs fabricated by AFRL on silicon-on-diamond substrates. This previous work utilized

phonon-heating mobility models to match DC IVs to predict substrate thermal resistance. The time transient simulations required heat capacity considerations and thermal resistance predictions in addition to the previous DC analysis [2]. This analysis investigates thermal transient changes in the order of nanoseconds to milliseconds. Our intent was to understand the effect of thermal time constants on the current capability of a GaN HEMT during low frequency modulation. Trapping effects were not included, therefore all effects are solely from thermal heating. The structure is modeled in 2D as a single 0.35 μm x 300 μm gate [3]. The device structure and substrate is composed of AlGaN, GaN, AlN, silicon and diamond described in other work [3]. The region below the diamond is modeled as a thermal resistance to a 300°K thermal potential. The simulation interfaced the 2D device simulation by the Silvaco ATLAS code and MixedMode circuit simulation. The Figure 1 shows just the channel region modeled for comparisons to other figures.

Figure 1 – Cross section of the modeled HEMT.

IV. Results

A. Virtual modeling of MIL-STD 750D Method 3104 in the time domain.

This technique uses a constant current on the gate electrode and predicts temperature due to the change in gate voltage dependence on temperature after the drain is pulsed for 100 μs [4]. The voltage pulse on

the drain is the “heating” pulse. A virtual calibration is performed by varying the global temperature and plotting the HEMT’s gate voltage. After the drain is pulsed the gate voltage variation is looked up against the calibration to predict a temperature. The electro-thermal simulation of the HEMT allows the temperature to be monitored in various regions. Thus a channel temperature predicted by this method can be compared to the TCAD temperature profile of the HEMT model to locate which region in the HEMT would corresponds to this predicted temperature. Figure 2 illustrates the location inside the gate electrode that correspond to the temperature predicted using Method 3104. This location does not remain in a constant position after the heating pulse is completed, but migrates higher into the electrode as shown by the points up to 3 us after the 100 us heating pulse is completed.

Figure 2 – The box defines the temperature location in a GaN HEMT corresponding to Method 3104. This is a closeup view of the gate electrode region.

For further examination, we used the code to monitor the average temperature of each material region in the HEMT (AlGaIn, GaN, AlN, Si and Diamond). We observed that the AlGaIn region (due to higher thermal resistance and lower heat capacity) attained a 40°C higher temperature than the lower regions during the heating pulse, and equalized with the other region temperatures within 10 us after the heating pulse. An estimation of the thermal time constants by each regions R_{TH} and heat capacity was on the order of 200-450 us.

B. Heating by Multiple Pulses

As an extension of the simulation of Method 3104, a 500KHz pulse train was examined to determine the thermal time constants for the HEMT to settle to an equilibrium temperature. The study investigated pulse trains out to 1 millisecond. During each 2 us period the device peak temperature would vary by

approximately 30°C degrees. The temperature variation impacts drain current as shown in Figure 3. Figure 3 depicts the change in drain current between a single 20us pulse or multiple 1us 50% duty cycle pulses. Results are solely related to self-heating on the microsecond time scale.

Figure 3 – HEMT drain current versus time comparing single 2us pulse (red) and multiple 2us pulses at 500 KHz (green).

Figure 4 illustrates the peak temperature variation in the HEMT switching at 500KHz for 100us.

The data of Figure 4 when fit to the equation $Temperature = 1 - e^{-t/\tau}$ the predicted thermal time constant τ is 74 us. This time constant corresponded to both the peak temperature and drain current (not shown). The first pulse has an average power of 3.57W, however it is also noted that due to the HEMT self-heating at 240 us the average power is reduced by 20% to 2.84W.

C. Comparison of equivalent average power at DC and 500 KHz.

The simulations modeling the 500KHz pulses was extrapolated to an equilibrium temperature and drain current to compare to a DC case at the same dissipated power. The cases were compared for an

average power of 7.9 W/mm. The 500 KHz, 1 us pulse at thermal equilibrium attains a temperature of 403°K whereas the DC static simulation for equivalent power reaches a peak temperature of 527°K. The peak temperature in the DC case is 124°C greater than operating at 500 KHz. The comparison is performed for equivalent power, but not equivalent average/DC drain current. The average pulsed and DC currents were 0.47 A and 0.17A respectively for the 300 um gate width device. To further understand the transient behavior of the pulsed simulation to reach thermal equilibrium. It was expected that the temperature profile may be similar to the DC analysis profile at times on the order of milliseconds.

D. Effects of channel joule heating and gate electrode heat capacity.

To examine the temperature profile, a single 10V 1ms pulse was applied to the drain to observe the temperature profile at a thermal equilibrium with the transient simulation. The 1 ms temperature profile is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Temperature profile at 1 ms, with a 6°C gradient with the transient simulation.

The peak temperature of the pulsed case is similar to the DC temperature profile as shown in Figure 6. The 1 ms snapshot is about 20°C lower, but the gradients over 1 micron are close, 6 to 8 degrees C.. The DC result shows the highest thermal potential to the drain side of the gate. The profile in Figure 5 (the pulsed case) which includes heat capacity effects (unlike the DC simulation) has the peak temperature in the same vicinity, but the temperature peak is broad due to the thermal storage of the gate electrode.

Investigating the temperature profile at sub-microsecond times shows a phenomenon that can not be presently observed experimentally or via a DC simulation. The joule heating of the channel was observed to occur for this particular bias example in the gate-to-source and gate-to-drain regions of the channel. This is where the current density is the

highest in the channel. For this bias, the current density directly under the gate electrode in the channel is spread out due to the gate depletion, thus the source and drain sides experience higher joule heating in the channel.

Figure 6 – Temperature profile of DC simulation, with a 8°C gradient with the transient simulation.

Therefore in a DC simulation and most analyses the heat source in the transistor is treated as a single heat source. There may be cases where the channel includes two point heat sources as shown in Figure 7. This is only observed in times shorter than the thermal time constant of the upper regions of the transistors, which occurs before thermal equilibrium.

Figure 7 – Temperature profile at 515 ns with 53°C gradient. Note the joule heating occurs where current density is highest, but differs at 1 ms as in Figure 5.

The heat generation is only part of the effect in Figure 7. Additionally the gate electrode’s heat capacity (in this simulation the material is Au) is higher than the surrounding materials, thus the thermal time constant of the gate electrode lags the channel and passivation regions. At half of a microsecond the gate electrode has minimal change (~8°C) in its thermal potential, while the AlGaN and GaN channel regions between gate-source and gate-drain has increased 61°C over the initial condition.

Thus for the HEMT's switching-on thermal differences of $\sim 50^\circ\text{C}/\mu\text{m}$ may be capable in the first microseconds.

V. Conclusions

To our knowledge this is the first TCAD analysis of self heating in the time domain for a GaN HEMT. Several points can be made on the significance of these results which can help advance the field to understand reliability of GaN RF devices under various electrical and thermal conditions.

A. Examination of utilizing the HEMT's gate diode voltage measurement to predict device temperature.

The simulation exercise performed Method 3104 virtually to provide perception to which location the method's temperature prediction corresponds to. This study's results locates the predicted temperature to occur at the section of the gate electrode closest to the devices channel. If Method 3104 is feasible to estimate HEMT channel temperatures, utilizing TCAD modeling in the time domain may provide a technique to create temperature gradients within various regions in the HEMT.

B. Observation of large temperature gradients between gate and spacing regions in sub microsecond time scales.

We observe that initial joule heating of the HEMT occurs in the two spacing regions where the current density is higher than directly below the gate. At tens of microseconds the two "hot spots" merge into one heat point source located at the drain side of the gate, and thermal energy is stored in the gate electrode. A DC simulation does not observe this condition, nor include heat capacity effects related to the gate electrode. Such a high temperature gradient in submicrosecond time scale may induce failure mechanisms in certain modulation cases.

VI. References

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